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Unemployment, Inflation, and Economic Growth: Evidence from Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Unemployment and inflation are serious determinants of underdevelopment in any nation, including Nigeria. The Johansen co-integration procedure and the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) were used to examine the impact of unemployment and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria. Annual data from 1981 to 2022 on Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Unemployment Rate (UER), Inflation Rate (IFR), and Government Expenditure (GEX) obtained mainly from the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin were employed in this investigation. The result of the ADF test confirms the stationarity of the selected variables at level and first difference, respectively, while the Johansen co-integration test result shows that a long-run relationship exists among the variables. The short-run results from the empirical analysis indicated that both the unemployment rate and inflation rate had an inverse and insignificant relationship with real gross domestic product in Nigeria. This insignificant impact is not unexpected since unemployment and inflation slow the growth and development of Nigeria's economy. The results also showed that government expenditure is directly and significantly responsible for explaining the economic growth in Nigeria. The result also shows that there was a slow adjustment process in the growth of the Nigerian economy since the speed of adjustment was approximately 45.1 per cent. The diagnostic test results confirmed the robustness of the model over time. The study recommends that governments at all levels should develop more effective and result-driven policies to address these problems of unemployment and inflation in Nigeria.

Keywords: Unemployment Rate, Inflation Rate, Government Expenditure, Real GDP, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

In the last few years, the caption that has covered the headline of newspapers, economic forums, one-to-one interviews, panel interviews, government agenda and so on has meandered around high unemployment and inflation rate, low or negative gross domestic product growth rate, corruption, civil wars, insurgency to mention a few in Nigeria and few other African countries (Ditimi et al., 2018). Also, economists have tried to establish the relationship between unemployment and inflation over time; however, they have concluded that the two variables are linked economically. The relationship between them is inversely correlated; therefore, when unemployment is high, inflation is low, and vice versa (Umaru & Zubairu, 2012). In any economy, inflation and unemployment are always on the front burner, and all economies always intend to keep both unemployment and inflation at a low rate, mostly on a single-digit rate, because this will tend to bring about stability in the macroeconomic policies

of the country. Macroeconomic stability is essential for growth, planning, and development. This stability is pivotal to effectively achieve the growth and development of Nigeria's economy (Orji et al., 2015). Unemployment and Inflation are serious determinants of underdevelopment in any nation, including Nigeria. The Nigerian economy has not been impressive despite the huge human and natural resources. The Nigerian economy is characterized by low per capita income, a high level of inflation, unemployment, and many socio-economic challenges. The economy has continued to witness economic recovery, which is immediately followed by economic recession (Adebayo & Ogunrinola, 2006).

Achieving the macroeconomic goals of any country involves maintaining price stability, achieving full employment, and attaining the highest level of growth and development. The second goal, which is achieving full employment, means maintaining a zero-unemployment level. This is because full employment is the absence of unemployment of any kind. But it is a clear fact that zero unemployment cannot be achieved by any country, because there is always a level of voluntary unemployment (Onwachukwu, 2015). Unemployment is an important determinant of the level of growth and development that a country can attain. According to Onwachukwu (2015), a country cannot claim to be developing and yet experience a high level of poverty, unemployment, inflation, and inequality. This shows the important role unemployment and inflation play in the process of economic growth.

Unemployment and inflation are major problems in almost all countries of the world, both in industrially advanced and poor countries. During the period of recession, an economy usually experiences a relatively high unemployment rate. There remains considerable theoretical debate regarding the causes, consequences, and solutions for unemployment and inflation. High unemployment rate signals a deficiency in the labour market, deepening poverty, and spreading an indecent standard of living (Olawale, 2015). Nigeria, being part of the global community, has its own share of the problem of unemployment and inflation since the cankerworms have been on a steady rise in the recent past.

Babalola et al. (2015) reported the work of Jayathileke and Rathnayake (2013), saying that most developing countries (like Nigeria) are easily affected by supply shocks, which leads to high variability in inflation, hence disturbing the consumption, investment, and production behaviour. However, due to government intervention in the financial and goods markets, macroeconomic reactions may cause economic instability and market failure. Although mild inflation is a healthy and natural phenomenon of any developing economy, no matter how strong and stable it may be (Aurangzeb & Asif, 2013). Thus, it could be said that a slight inflation is greasing the wheels of commerce. The risk attached to this is that stable prices and zero inflation rates might trigger deflation, economic depression, general recession, technical insolvency, and even bankruptcy. Economists have diverse views about the concept of inflation. Economic performance has not been highly impressive. The continued economic crisis, with the associated problems of high inflationary pressure, high exchange rate, debt overhang, adverse balance of payment, and high inflation rates, has been on the increase. Against a high rate of unemployment and underemployment, a large public sector, low wages, and poor working conditions have been premised on a high inflation rate in Nigeria. Also, underemployment and unemployment are prominent features of the informal labour market as well. Consequently, the full potential of a labour-surplus economy has not been fully exploited (Adebayo, 2010).

The overall aim of this study is to examine the impact of unemployment and inflation on Nigeria's economic growth. The specific objectives are to examine:

1. The extent to which the unemployment rate impacts the Real Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria
2. The effect of the inflation rate on the Real Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria
3. The relationship between government expenditure and Real Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Clarification

Concept of Unemployment and Inflation

Unemployment and inflation are concepts that have been subjected to many definitions depending on how the various authors tend to view them. According to Abdulsalam and Abdullahi (2016), unemployment is

often defined by the classical economists as the excess supply of labour over the demand for labour, which is caused by an adjustment in real wage. The Classical or real-wage unemployment occurs when real wages for a job are set above the market-clearing level, causing the number of job-seekers to exceed the number of vacancies. Unemployment, as defined by the International Labour Organization (2009), is a state of joblessness that occurs when people are without jobs and have actively sought work within the past four weeks. Unemployment is a measure of the prevalence of people unemployed, and it is calculated as a percentage by dividing the number of unemployed individuals by the number of individuals currently in the labour force.

In the view of Olaiya (2013), any population of jobless people can be said to be unemployed, which has rendered many young men and women redundant. Ojo (1998) defines unemployment as the idleness of the man who depends on employment for a livelihood and cannot get the type of employment for which he is suited when he wants the kind of employment, and he is fit for it. Thus, unemployment is a condition where a person has the ability to work to earn a living, but a job is not available for them. Such people may be those who have completed primary, secondary, or tertiary education, who are roaming on the streets searching for what to do for a living.

Unemployment is a social phenomenon. It is one of the most persistent and unmanageable problems facing Less Developed Countries of the world. Nigeria is not an exception in this regard. In recent times, the incidence of unemployment in Nigeria has been deeply and widely spread, cutting across all age groups, educational strata, and geographical entities. This negative development will partly explain the level of economic activity in countries around the world. The problem of unemployment is one of the serious impediments to social progress in Nigeria, apart from the huge waste of resources; it generates human welfare loss in terms of lower output, thereby leading to lower income (Jibir et al., 2015).

The concept of inflation has been defined as a persistent rise in the general price level of a broad spectrum of goods and services in a country over a long period of time. Inflation has been intrinsically linked to money, as captured by the often-heard maxim 'inflation is too much money chasing too few goods' (Mohammed et al., 2015). According to Balami (2006), inflation is a situation of a rising general price level of a broad spectrum of goods and services over a long period of time. It is measured as the rate of increase in the general price level over a specific period of time. To the neo-classical and their followers at the University of Chicago, inflation is fundamentally a monetary phenomenon. In the words of Friedman (1976), inflation is always and everywhere a monetary phenomenon and can be produced only by a more rapid increase in the quantity of money than output. Inflation and unemployment have been seen to be serious determinants of underdevelopment in any nation, including Nigeria. The Nigerian economy has not been impressive despite the huge human and natural resources. The Nigerian economy is characterized by low per capita income, a high level of inflation and unemployment, and many socio-economic challenges. The economy has continued to witness economic recovery, which is immediately followed by economic recession and depression (Mohammed et al., 2015).

Concept of Economic Growth

Economic growth, according to Jhingan (2003), is the process whereby the real per capita income of a country increases over a long period of time, and is measured by the increase in the amount of goods and services produced in a country. A growing economy produces more goods and services in each successive time period. Thus, in a wider perspective, it implies raising the standard of living of the people and reducing the inequality of income distribution. In the words of Zhattau (2013), economic growth is the basis of increased prosperity, and it comes from the accumulation of more capital and innovations, which lead to technical progress, an idea similar to the Solow growth model, which sees economic growth in terms of growth in total GDP due to an increase in population, technical progress, and investment. Growth, according to Classical Economists, signifies an increase in the rate of investment (Abdulsalam & Abdullahi, 2016). In other words, growth is a function of the share of profit in the national income. There exists a positive relationship between a higher rate of profit and a higher rate of growth in the long run. Economic growth is often measured by the increase in GDP (Owamah & Mgbomene, 2025; Owamah,

2025). A country is said to experience growth if its total output goes up over a certain time (Owamah & Mgbomene, 2025; Owamah et al., 2025).

Theoretical Review

Endogenous Growth Theory

Endogenous growth theories describe economic growth that is generated by factors within the production process, such as economies of scale, increasing returns, or induced technological changes, as opposed to exogenous factors such as an increase in population. When endogenous growth models are set within a monetary exchange framework of Lucas (1988), Lucas and Stokey (1987), McCallum and Goodfriend (1987), the inflation rate (tax) lowers both the return on all capital and the growth rate. According to Gokal and Hamif (2004), a rise in inflation reduces the marginal value of today.

The Phillips Curve

Hussein (2014) reported that in 1958, the Zealander economist William Phillips carried out an empirical study of the British economy, using data for the period from 1861 to 1957. This study estimates the relationship between the unemployment rate and the rate of change in the money wage as an indicator of inflation, given that wages represent a large proportion of the cost and thus the price. The results of the study reveal the presence of a trade-off between the unemployment rate and the rate of change in wages as a representative of the rate of inflation.

Phelps interpreted the result of the study, that in booms, the demand for labor increases and the unemployment rate decreases, then workers have the opportunity to request higher wages. In periods of depression, the demand for labor decreases, and the unemployment rate increases. Then, the ability of workers to demand higher wages is limited, and the decrease in wage rate increases significantly.

This finding supports Keynesian thought; therefore, several economists in the United States were encouraged to measure the relationship between inflation and unemployment using data on the U.S. economy. The studies revealed the inverse relationship between the two variables, which led to consolidating the results of Phelps' study and dubbed this relationship the Phillips curve.

In the 1970s, the industrialized nations experienced an economic phenomenon called stagflation, which means that the economy is suffering from an increase in both the unemployment rate and the inflation rate at the same time. This phenomenon has cast doubt on the Keynesian thought and the Phillips curve. Thus, there is no permanent inverse relationship between inflation and unemployment, but it may be a positive relationship. This phenomenon has been interpreted by several economists, who linked it to the rise in oil prices during that period and, therefore, the high cost of production, which led to a change in aggregate supply and thus lower output, with a rising unemployment rate associated with a rise in prices. Another explanation indicates that the inverse relationship between inflation and unemployment rate as represented by Phelps curve is only a short-term relationship and unstable, because it prevails for a limited period of time and there are factors lead to trans Phelps curve to another situation, and the major

factor that leads to instability is unexpected inflation where the real wage for workers is declining, which motivates them to demand higher nominal wage, as a result the business will reduce the demand for labor, which increases unemployment. So, unexpected inflation is accompanied by an increase in the unemployment rate.

The original Phillips Curve idea was criticized by the Monetarist school among them Milton Friedman, Friedman accepted that the short run Phillips Curve existed – but for the long run, he introduced the concept of the NAIUR, Which is defined as the rate of unemployment when the rate of wage inflation is stable, and argued that Phillips curve in the long-run takes a vertical situation on the horizontal axis (rate of unemployment) and be parallel to the rate of inflation axis to indicate there is no trade-off between unemployment and inflation.

The monetarist said that increasing AD to promote economic growth and lower unemployment has a short-run effect on jobs. So, a government could not permanently drive unemployment below the NAIUR because it would lead to higher inflation, which would finally lead to higher unemployment accompanied by increasing expected inflation. Thus, the long-run Phillips Curve is normally drawn as vertical – but it can shift inwards over time.

Such a change could happen if the economic policies achieve a vital reduction in the natural rate of unemployment as a result of reducing frictional and structural unemployment.

Empirical Literature

Okoroafor et al. (2018) examined the causal relationship between inflation and economic growth as well as estimating threshold and forecasting of inflation in Nigeria for the period 1961 – 2016 and the results showed that inflation does not Granger cause economic growth and neither does economic growth granger cause inflation during the period of study but an inflation threshold of 14% -15% both in the short run and long run was established for Nigeria. Babalola et al. (2015) empirically studied the effect of inflation and interest rate on economic growth in Nigeria between 1981 and 2014 using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method and found that Inflation and Interest rate hurt Economic growth, but neither Inflation nor Interest rate granger causes economic growth. They concluded with the recommendation that policymakers should focus on maintaining inflation at a low rate (single digit) and ensuring interest rate stability.

Gatawa et al. (2017) study on the impact of money supply and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria from 1973-2013 using the VAR Model and Granger Causality test within an error correction framework revealed a positive impact of broad money supply, while inflation and interest rate hurt growth, mostly in the long run. The short-run parsimonious results revealed that, except for inflation, broad money supply and interest rate were negatively related to economic growth, while the results of the causality tests revealed that none of the explanatory variables Granger causes economic growth, implying that money supply, inflation, and interest rate have not influenced growth. The study therefore recommended an expansionary monetary policy, zero-interest-based finance capable of attracting investment in the real sector of the economy and arresting the inflationary tendency associated with monetary policy.

Ditimi et al. (2018) empirically investigated the influence of money supply on inflation in Nigeria with the employment of the co-integration test and error correction approach on annual time series data spanning from 1970 to 2016 to ascertain both the long-run and short-run dynamic relationships among the variables under consideration. Their findings showed that money supply does not considerably influence inflation both in the long and short run, possibly because the country is in recession. The Granger causality outcome demonstrates that there is no causality between money supply and inflation in Nigeria within the study period and vice versa.

Rabiul et al. (2017) examined the determinants of factors that affect inflation in Malaysia using a consistent quantitative method and the econometric model to identify the relationship between inflation (dependent variable) and Money Supply, Exchange Rate, and Unemployment Rate (independent variables), which were categorized as mathematical model and econometric model. The results revealed that high inflation may have a negative impact on a particular country.

Saad and Suryati (2014) showed in their work on the effect of real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) on unemployment in Nigeria using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach. Their results revealed a positive relationship between unemployment and real GDP in Nigeria, both in the short run and in the long run. The study concludes that real GDP growth causes unemployment in Nigeria.

Sahin (2016) analyzed the determinants of unemployment in China over the period of 1982-2014 by examining the empirical relationship among unemployment, gross domestic product, foreign direct investment, and inflation rate using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach. The long-run estimated results reveal that GDP has a negative and significant relationship with the unemployment rate in China. Inflation rate and foreign direct investment have a positive and insignificant relationship with unemployment rate, while the short-run results show that GDP, inflation, and foreign direct investment have a negative and insignificant relationship with unemployment rate. Olawale (2015) focused on the impact of selected macro-economic variables on unemployment rate in Nigeria using the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) approach and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to calculate the Forecast Error Variance Decomposition (FEVD) as well as the Granger causality test to know the variables that are informative in forecasting the unemployment rate. The results revealed that positive shocks to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) increased the unemployment rate, while Shocks to Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Inflation Rate (INF), and Money Supply (M2) reduced the unemployment rate. He added that shocks to the Lending Rate (LR) reduce the unemployment rate.

Echekoba et al. (2015) worked on inflation and growth in developing countries, especially in Nigeria, with the view of ascertaining the relationship between inflation and economic growth, as well as the inflationary effect and the means of controlling inflation on Nigeria's economic growth. Their study covered the ten years from 2002 to 2012 and adopted an expos-facto research design using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression technique, and the results showed that inflation hurts the exchange rate, consumer price index (CPI), and economic growth in Nigeria, but revealed a positive relationship between inflation and gross domestic product (GDP) in Nigeria.

IMETHODOLODY

Model Specification

The specification of Abdulsalam and Abdullahi (2016) on which this work is mainly hinged is presented as follows:

$$RGDP = f(\text{UNEMPL}, \text{INFL}) \quad (3.1)$$

$$RGDP = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \text{UNEMPL} + \beta_3 \text{INFL} + \mu \quad (3.2)$$

Where:

RGDP = Rate of GDP growth,

UNEMPL=Unemployment rate and

INFL=Inflation rate.

The model for the current study is stated thus:

$$\ln GDP_t = f(\text{UER}_t, \text{IFR}_t, \ln \text{GEX}_t) \quad (3.3)$$

The linear relationship of equation (3.4) could be stated as:

$$\ln GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{UER}_t + \beta_2 \text{IFR}_t + \beta_3 \ln \text{GEX}_t + U_t \quad (3.4)$$

(Apriori expectation $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0$)

Where:

$\ln RGDP$ = log of Real Gross Domestic Product, UER = Unemployment Rate, IFR = Inflation Rate, $\ln GEX$ = log of Government Expenditure, U = Disturbance term or error term, β_0 = Intercept, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Coefficient of the independent variables, and t is the time trend.

Sources of Data and Variables Description

Data for this study were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics Statistical Bulletin from 1981 to 2022. Below is the description of the variables sourced and used for this study: GDP at Constant Basic Prices (otherwise known as the Real GDP) equals GDP at Constant Market Prices less indirect taxes net of subsidies. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is the monetary value of goods and services produced in an economy during a period of time, irrespective of the nationality of the people who produced the goods and services. It is calculated without making deductions for depreciation.

Unemployment Rate (UER): This represents the total number of the economically active population who are without work but available for and seeking work, including people who have lost their jobs and those who have voluntarily left work (Asoluka & Okezie, 2011).

Inflation (IFR): Inflation is a situation that occurs when the general level of prices rises rapidly and persistently over a period of time. In theory, the relationship between inflation and economic growth is a controversial one, as economists have not agreed on the nature of the relationship (Okosodo and Mamudu, 2018).

Government Expenditure (GEX): This is total government spending on both recurrent and capital projects and programmes in Nigeria. Oyeyemi and Awujola (2014) clarified that government expenditure improves the level of economic growth through policy implementation efforts, projects, and programmes.

Method of Data Analysis

The method used in analysing the data collected for this research is basically descriptive and statistical in nature. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test statistic was employed to perform the stationarity test. Statistical theory requires that variables be stationary before the application of standard econometric techniques. This was done to avoid spurious (misleading) results. The Johansen cointegration test was

also conducted to examine the existence or otherwise of a long-run relationship among the variables in the models. The error correction model was thereafter estimated to determine the speed of adjustment to the long-run equilibrium. Diagnostic and stability tests were also performed to confirm the robustness of the model.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unit Root Test

The stationarity status of the selected economic indicators (Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP), Unemployment Rate (UER), Inflation Rate (IFR), and Total Government Expenditure (GEX)) was examined using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic. The results, which are displayed in Table 4.1 below, show that all the selected variables (RGDP, UER, and GEX) were stationary at first difference I (1) except IFR, which was stationary at the level. In other words, IFR was found to be stationary at I (0).

Table 4.1: Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Level	First Difference	Order of Integration
lnRGDP	-0.797472 (0.8054)	-5.459930 (0.0001)	I (1)
UER	-1.540173 (0.5022)	-7.618647 (0.0000)	I (1)
IFR	-3.254075 (0.0249)	-6.531264 (0.0000)	I (0)
lnGEXP	-0.257113 (0.9214)	-7.621081 (0.0000)	I (1)
5%CV	-2.945842	5% = -2.948404	

Source: Author’s compilation with information from stationarity test results

Note: *MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values are reported in parentheses.

ADF test statistic was compared to the 5 per cent critical value (C.V).

Cointegration Test using the Johansen Methodology

The results of the Unrestricted Cointegration Rank tests for the model are presented in Table 4.2 below. Starting with the null hypothesis that there are no cointegrating vector in the model, the results show that there exists at least one cointegrating relationship in the model as both the Trace and Max-Eigen statistics rejected the null against the alternative at 5 per cent level of significance which shows that there is a unique long run relationship between Unemployment Rate (UER), Inflation Rate (IFR), Total Government Expenditure (GEX) and Real Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria (see the table below).

Table 4.2: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test result for the model

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Trace Stat.	Critical Value (0.05)	Prob**	Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Max-Eigen Stat.	Critical Value (0.05)	Prob**
None *	57.61612	47.85613	0.0047	None *	27.98229	27.58434	0.0445
At most 1	29.63383	29.79707	0.0522	At most 1	17.16089	21.13162	0.1645
At most 2	12.47294	15.49471	0.1356	At most 2	11.15160	14.26460	0.1468
At most 3	1.321340	3.841466	0.2504	At most 3	1.321340	3.841466	0.2504

Source: Author’s compilation with information from unrestricted cointegration rank results.

Note: Both Trace and Max-Eigenvalue tests indicate 1 cointegrating equation at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level and

** Mackinnon p-values

Error Correction Representation (Short-run)

The results of the error correction representation of the model are reported in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Error Correction Representation of the Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1410.190	249.9450	5.642002	0.0000
D(UER)	-36.31536	75.37902	-0.481770	0.6334
D(IFR)	-9.229680	15.24192	-0.605546	0.5492
D(GEX)	0.500605	0.153203	3.267593	0.0041
ECM (-1)	-0.451071	0.201570	-2.237788	0.0038

Source: Author’s compilation with information from ECM results.

Table 4.3 reports the results of the short-run error correction model. The result showed that the unemployment rate (UER) has a direct and insignificant relationship with real gross domestic product in Nigeria. This finding supports the work of Jibir et al. (2015) and Mohammed et al. (2015). Interestingly, a unit change in unemployment rate in Nigeria leads to a 36.31536 increase in RGDP.

Empirical evidence showed that the inflation rate (IFR) has an inverse and insignificant impact on real gross domestic product in Nigeria. This shows that as inflation declines, more money is invested into production to boost economic growth and development. This finding supports the work of Oyeyemi and Awujola (2014), Mohammed et al. (2015), and Gatawa et al. (2017) that if a country has an average inflation of more than 15 per cent (high inflation), any further increase leads to a decrease in the real gross domestic product. Interestingly, a unit change in the inflation rate in Nigeria reduces RGDP by -9.229680%.

The coefficient of government expenditure (GEX) is 1.226388. This implies that there is a direct relationship between government expenditure and real gross domestic product, and a 1 per cent change in government expenditure raised gross domestic product by 1.226388 per cent. This result is consistent with previous studies of Oyeyemi and Awujola (2014); Jibir et al. (2015); Mohammed et al. (2015).

Finally, the ECM, which is -0.451071, is statistically significant and has the appropriate sign (negative). It suggests, however, that there is a low adjustment process in real gross domestic product since the speed of adjustment is approximately 45.1 per cent. It is also a confirmation that real gross domestic product, unemployment, inflation rate, and government expenditure are cointegrated.

4.4 Diagnostic Test

To confirm the robustness of the model, a diagnostic test was performed as shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Key Regression and Diagnostic Statistics for the Model

R-squared	0.620522	Mean dependent var	1478.694
Adjusted R-squared	0.503007	S.D. dependent var	1527.291
S.E. of regression	1446.492	Akaike info criterion	17.51992
Sum squared resid	64862.48	Schwarz criterion	17.73985
Log likelihood	-310.3585	Hannan-Quinn criterion	17.59668
F-statistic	28.00482	Durbin-Watson stat	1.937307
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000312		

Source: Author's compilation with information from ECM results

The coefficient of determination R² indicates that 62.1 per cent of the total variation of real gross domestic product is jointly explained by unemployment, inflation rate, and government expenditure. The Akaike information criterion, Schwarz criterion, and Hannan-Quinn criterion showed that the model is correctly specified. The F statistic measuring the joint significance of all regressors in the model is statistically significant at the 5 per cent level. Similarly, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.937307 confirms that the autocorrelation problem is eliminated.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of unemployment and inflation rate on economic growth in Nigeria. Real gross domestic product is influenced by several factors, which include unemployment, inflation rate, interest rate, exchange rate, and government expenditure, among others, which were reviewed under conceptual, theoretical, and empirical literature. However, there have been various debates on the impact of these variables on real gross domestic product in Nigeria. Hence, the main objective is to examine the impact of unemployment and inflation rate on Nigerian economic growth. Annual time series data from 1981 to 2018 on Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Unemployment Rate (UER), Inflation Rate (IFR), and Government Expenditure (GEX) used in this work were obtained mainly from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2018).

The empirical study on the impact of unemployment and inflation rates on Nigeria's economic growth from 1981 to 2018 confirms the stationarity of the selected economic variables at level 1(0) and first difference 1(1), respectively. The Johansen cointegration test indicates a long-run relationship between

UER, IFR, GEX, and RGDP. Unemployment rate had a direct and insignificant relationship with real gross domestic product in Nigeria, while the inflation rate was found to be inversely related but insignificant in explaining the growth rate in the Nigerian economy. Government expenditure was found to have a direct and significant relationship with real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

The error correction mechanism revealed a slow adjustment process of the selected macroeconomic indicators on real gross domestic product in Nigeria, as the speed of adjustment to the long-run equilibrium relationship is approximately 45.1 per cent. The diagnostic test conducted confirmed the robustness of the model over time.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. To achieve the macroeconomic goals of our country, Nigeria, the government should make effective policies to maintain price stability and reduce the unemployment rate, which will aid economic growth and sustainable development.
2. Solving the problem of unemployment, governments at all levels should develop more effective and result-driven policies to arrest this problem, such as on-the-job training and learning skill development.
3. The government should increase its budget on capital expenditure to enable a geometric spread of infrastructural facilities, which will eventually boost and influence economic growth in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Abdulsalam, S. A., & Abdullahi, B. (2016). The impact of unemployment and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981–2014. *International Journal of Business and Economic Sciences Applied Research*, 9(1), 47–55. Retrieved June 28, 2018, from <http://ijbesar.teicmt.gr>
- Adebayo, A. (2010). Youth unemployment and the National Directorate of Employment self-employment programmes. *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*.
- Adebayo, A., & Ogunrinola, I. O. (2006). Contemporary dimensions of unemployment problem in Nigeria: A special challenge under the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy. *Nigerian Economic Society Conference Proceedings*, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Ahmed, S., & Mortaza, G. (2005). *Inflation and economic growth in Bangladesh: 1981–2005* (PAU Working Paper No. 0604).
- Aiyedogbon, J. O., & Ohwofasa, B. O. (2012). Poverty and youth unemployment in Nigeria, 1987–2011. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(20), 269–279.
- Amassoma, D., & Nwosa, P. I. (2013). The impact of unemployment rate on productivity growth in Nigeria: An error correction modeling approach. *International Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(8), 1–13.
- Aminu, U., & Anono, A. Z. (2012). An empirical analysis of the relationship between unemployment and inflation in Nigeria from 1977–2009. *Journal of Economics and Financial Review*, 1(12), 42–61. <http://www.businessjournalz.org/efr>
- Aminu, U., & Manu, D. (2014). The growth effects of unemployed resources and inflation in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(2).
- Aqil, M., Qureshi, M., Ahmed, R., & Qadeer, S. (2014). Determinants of unemployment in Pakistan. *International Journal of Physical and Social Sciences*, 4(4), 676–682.
- Arslan, M., & Zaman, R. (2014). Unemployment and its determinants: A study of Pakistan economy (1999–2010). *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(13), 20–24.
- Asoluka, N., & Okezie, A. I. (2011). Unemployment and Nigerian economic growth (1985–2009). In *Proceedings of the 2011 International Conference on Teaching, Learning and Change* (pp. 1–11).
- Aurangzeb, A., & Asif, K. (2013). Factors effecting unemployment: A cross-country analysis. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 219–230.
- Babalola, O. O., Danladi, J. D., Akomolafe, K. J., & Ajiboye, O. P. (2015). Inflation, interest rates and economic growth in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(30), 91–102.
- Bakare, A. S. (2012). Stabilization policy, unemployment crises and economic growth in Nigeria. *Universal Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 2(4).
- Balami, D. H. (2006). *Macroeconomic theory and practice*. Salawe Prints.
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2017). *Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin* (Vol. 28).
- Chang-Shuai, L., & Zi-juan, L. (2012). Study on the relationship among Chinese unemployment rate, economic growth and inflation. *Advances in Applied Economics and Finance*, 1(1), 1–6.
- Ditimi, A., Keji, S., & Emma-Ebere, O. (2018). The influence of money supply on inflation in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 31(1), 5–23.
- O'Sullivan, A., & Sheffrin, S. M. (2003). *Economics: Principles in action*. Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Echekoba, F. N., Adigwe, P. K., & Amakor, I. (2015). Inflation and growth in developing countries: The Nigerian experience. *Journal of Business and Management*, 17(2), 95–109.
- Essien, A. E. (2001). Nigeria's economic growth: Performance and determinants. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review*, 40(3), 16–39.
- Essien, S. N., Many, G. A., Arigo, M. O., Bassey, K. J., Ogunyinka, S. F., Ojegwo, D. G., & Ogbuehi, F. (2016). Monetary policy and unemployment in Nigeria: Is there a dynamic relationship? *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 7(1), 207–231.

- Fakhri, H. (2011). Relationship between inflation and economic growth in Azerbaijani economy: Is there any threshold effect? *Asian Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 1(1).
- Fashoyin, T. (1986). *Incomes and inflation in Nigeria*. Longman Publishers.
- Fitsum, S. D., Yilkal, W. A., & Teshome, A. R. (2016). The relationship between inflation, money supply and economic growth in Ethiopia: Cointegration and causality analysis. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 6(1), 556–565.
- Fatukasi, B. (2012). Determinants of inflation in Nigeria: An empirical analysis. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(18), 262–271.
- Friedman, M. (1976). *Inflation and unemployment* (Nobel Memorial Lecture). University of Chicago.
- Gatawa, N. M., Abdulgafar, A., & Olarinde, M. O. (2017). Impact of money supply and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria (1973–2013). *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 8(3), 26–37.
- Gokal, V., & Hanif, S. (2004). *Relationship between inflation and economic growth*.
- Gur, B. (2015). An analysis of unemployment determinants in BRIC countries. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(1), 192–198.
- Gylych, J., Olanrewaju, J. O., & Abdurahman, I. (2016). Impact of inflation and unemployment on economic growth in selected member states of ECOWAS (2001–2014). *Advances in Economics and Business*, 4(5), 222–244.
- Hamilton, A. (2001). *Exploding inflation*. Zea Intelligence.
- Hussein, A. (2014). The trade-off between unemployment and inflation: Evidence from causality test for Jordan. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(4), 103–111.
- Hussein, A., & Saleh, A. (2015). Does Phillips curve really exist? An empirical evidence from Jordan. *European Scientific Journal*, 11(10), 253–275.
- International Labour Organization. (2009). *Labour statistics yearbook*. ILO.
- Jayathileke, J., & Rathnayake, R. (2013). Inflation, interest rates and economic growth in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(30), 91–102.
- Jhingan, M. L. (2003). *Advanced macroeconomic theory* (11th ed.). Vrinda Publications.
- Jibir, A., Bappayaya, B., & Babayo, H. (2015). Re-examination of the impact of unemployment on economic growth of Nigeria: An econometric approach. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(8), 116–123.
- Kareem, R. O. (2015). Employment level and economic growth of Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*, 8(1), 53–70.
- Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1).
- Lucas, R. E., Jr., & Stokey, N. L. (1987). Money and interest in a cash-in-advance economy. *Econometrica*, 55, 491–513.
- Mahmood, A., Akhtar, I., Qamar, N., Abbas, A., & Sana, S. (2014). Determinants of unemployment in Pakistan: A statistical study. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 4(12), 1163–1175.
- Maqbool, M., Mahmood, T., Sattar, A., & Bhalli, M. N. (2013). Determinants of unemployment: Empirical evidences from Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 51(2), 191–207.
- Masha, I. (2002). The dynamics of money, output and prices in Nigeria: Some neutrality propositions using the vector error correction specification. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review*, 40(2), 29–59.
- McCallum, B. T., & Goodfriend, M. S. (1987). Demand for money: Theoretical studies. In J. Eatwell, M. Millgate, & P. Newman (Eds.), *The new Palgrave: Money*. Macmillan Press.
- Mohammed, Y., Okoroafor, O. K. D., & Awe, E. O. (2015). Analysis of the relationship between inflation, unemployment and economic growth in Nigeria: 1987–2012. *Journal of Applied Economics and Finance*, 2(3), 102–109.
- Muhammad, S. (2014). Effects of inflation and unemployment on economic growth in Pakistan. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(15).
- Muhammad, S. (2014). Effects of inflation and unemployment on economic growth in Pakistan. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(15).
- Nwaobi, G. C. (2009). *Inflation, unemployment and Nigeria families: An empirical investigation* (MPR Paper No. 14596).
- Ojo, F. (1998). *Human resources management*. Allen Publishers.
- Okafor, E. E. (2011). Youth unemployment and implications for stability of democracy in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 13, 358–372.
- Okoroafor, O. K. D., Adeniji, S. O., & Olasehinde, T. (2018). Estimating and forecasting the impact of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria using threshold analysis. *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 9(1), 1–22.
- Okun, A. M. (1962). Potential GNP: Its measurement and significance. *Proceedings of the Business and Economic Statistics Section of the American Statistical Association*.
- Okosodo, L. A., & Mamudu, Z. U. (2018). Empirical investigation of the impact of deposit money banks credit on investment in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 7(1), 246–278.
- Oladeji, S. I. (1994). *Absorption of educated manpower into Nigeria's informal sector* (Diagnostic Studies Series 1). NMB.
- Olaiya, S. A. (2013). Towards Vision 20:2020: Need for attitudinal change emphasis on youth unemployment. *African Journal of Stability and Development*.
- Olawale, B. A. (2015). Impact of macroeconomic variables on Nigerian unemployment using the vector autoregressive approach. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies*, 2(12), 65–76.
- Omeke, P. C., & Ugwunyi, C. U. (2010). Money, price and output: A causality test for Nigeria. *American Journal of Scientific Research*, 8(1), 78–87.
- Oni, B. (2006). Employment generation in Nigeria: Theoretical and empirical issues. *Journal of Nigerian Economic Society*.
- Oniore, J., Bernard, A., & Gyang, E. (2015). Macroeconomic determinants of unemployment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 3(10), 215–230.
- Onwachukwu, C. I. (2015). Does unemployment significantly impact on economic growth in Nigeria? *Global Journal of Human-Social Science*, 15(8), 22–26.
- Osundina, C. K., Osundina, J. A., Jayeoba, O. O., & Olayinka, I. M. (2016). Exchange rate volatility and banks performance: Evidence from Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 2(4), 1–11.
- Orji, A., Orji-Anthony, L., & Okafor, J. (2015). Inflation and unemployment nexus in Nigeria: Another test of the Phillips curve. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 5(5), 766–778.

- Owamah, E. K., & Mgbomene, C. (2025). Exchange rate and Nigerian's economic performance. *Jalingo Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 6(4), 287–298.
- Owamah, E. K., & Mgbomene, C. (2025). Impact of oil and non-oil exports on Nigeria's economic growth. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 8(7), 4892–4902. <https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v8-i7-75>
- Owamah, E. K., Egbon, P. C., & Ishioro, B. O. (2025). Remittances and income inequality in selected countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 8(10), 6832–6844. <https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v8-i10-27>
- Owamah, E. K. (2025). The dominant impact of oil exports on economic growth in Nigeria: A comparative ARDL analysis with non-oil exports. *Journal of Economics, Business, and Commerce*, 2(2), 207–215. <https://doi.org/10.69739/jebc.v2i2.1082>
- Oyeyemi, A. O., & Awujola, A. (2014). An appraisal of some factors influencing economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies*, 3, 33–39.
- Patterson, N., Okafor, O., & Williams, D. (2006). Globalization and employment generation: Evaluating the impact of trade on aggregate employment in Nigeria's industrial sector. *Proceedings of the Nigerian Economic Society Annual Conference*, Abuja.
- Phillips, A. W. (1958). The relationship between unemployment and the rate of change in money wage rates in the United Kingdom. *Economica*, 25(100), 283–299.
- Popovic, G., & Popovic, J. (2009). Inflation and unemployment in the EU: Comparative analysis of Phillips regularity.
- Rabiul, I., Ahmad, B. A., Emil, M., & Narmatha, M. (2017). Determinants of factors affecting inflation in Malaysia. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 7(2), 355–364.
- Rafindadi, A. S. (2012). Macroeconomic policy, output and unemployment dynamics in Nigeria: Is there evidence of jobless growth? *Proceedings of the 53rd Annual Conference of the Nigerian Economic Society*, Abuja.
- Raheem, M. I. (1993). Nigeria for Africa: A case for labour export. In T. A. Oyejide & M. I. Obadan (Eds.), *Applied economics and economic policy in honour of Emmanuel C. Edozien*. University Press.
- Rashid, A., & Kernal, A. (1997). Macroeconomic policies and their impact on poverty alleviation in Pakistan. *Pakistan Development Review*, 36(1), 39–68.
- Sa'idu, B. M., & Muhammad, A. A. (2015). Do unemployment and inflation substantially affect economic growth? *Journal of Economics and Development Studies*, 3(2), 132–139.
- Saad, B., & Suryati, I. (2014). An analysis of the effect of real gross domestic product on unemployment in Nigeria: An ARDL approach. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(14), 7–13.
- Sahin, D. (2016). Determinants of unemployment: Empirical analysis for China. *The Journal of Academic Social Science*, 4(22), 50–58.
- Stock, J. H., & Watson, M. W. (1999). *Forecasting inflation* (NBER Working Paper No. 7023). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Subramaniam, T., & Baharumshah, A. (2011). Determinants of unemployment in the Philippines. *The Empirical Economics Letters*, 10(12), 1248–1257.
- Thayaparan, A. (2014). Impact of inflation and economic growth on unemployment in Sri Lanka: A study of time series analysis. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 13(5), 44–54.
- Totonchi, J. (2011). Macroeconomic theories of inflation. *International Conference on Economics and Finance*, 4(1), 459–462.
- Umaru, A., & Zubairu, A. (2012). Effect of inflation on the growth and development of the Nigerian economy: An empirical analysis. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(10).
- Umo, J. U. (1996). Introductory overview. In J. U. Umo (Ed.), *Towards full employment strategy in Nigeria*. National Manpower Board.
- Williams, O., & Adedeji, O. S. (2004). *Inflation dynamics in the Dominican Republic* (IMF Working Paper No. WP/04/29). International Monetary Fund.
- Zhattau, V. S. (2013). Fiscal policy as an engine of economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 2(2).